

Working Group Collaboration activities and mechanisms

DIHNET.EU aims at developing a set of tools and boosting the collaboration of the different Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs), DIH networks and other key DIH stakeholders in Europe. The DIHNET Working Groups (WG) will identify and target challenges that require the input from the DIH community and the different stakeholders in four main topics: “Finance and funding opportunities”, “Collaboration activities and mechanisms”, “Connection with policies and strategies” and “Business Models and Sustainability”.

Objectives

The objective of the Working Group on “Collaboration activities and mechanisms” is to address the challenges and barriers to improve DIHs collaboration; and to understand and exchange good practices that can feed the learning process. This WG focuses on cross-border collaboration as well as on the mechanisms and tools needed to ensure effective and sustainable cooperation.

What are the challenges?

- Linking the existing individual DIH structures, projects, initiatives, national and regional hubs, etc.
- Building a pan-European network of DIHs.
- Identifying and reaching the end-users of the DIHs.
- Identifying the tools needed and jointly develop them.

How the DIH community is going to address these challenges will be discussed in the working group.

How to get engaged with the WG

You can join the DIHNET.EU Community platform at www.dihnet.eu or contact the WG coordinator.

Marta Palau Franco
“Collaboration activities and mechanisms” WG Coordinator
marta.palaufranco@eu-robotics.net
+32 2 706 83 68

Join the
DIHNET.EU
online
Community!